

Exploring Innovations in Amphibious Drones: Advancing Dual-Environment Capabilities for Enhanced Surveillance - A Comprehensive Study

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Abstract— The drone possesses the capability to navigate both aerial and aquatic environments. Achieving buoyancy for water traversal necessitates careful consideration of the craft's balance and symmetry. Enhanced communication is imperative, requiring signals with improved penetration and reduced attenuation. To address this challenge, radio signals and acoustic communications are commonly employed in amphibious drones. Effectively managing drone movement entails utilizing a microcontroller as the flight controller for transmitting and storing user data. Additionally, amphibious drones utilize aluminum alloy construction to mitigate damage. Based on these requirements, we are currently developing an amphibious drone and assessing its performance both in air and water. Following thorough testing, the amphibious drone can be deployed for various applications including surveillance, research, and marine surveys. The ongoing development of the amphibious drone will undergo further evaluation in the future.

Keywords— Amphibious drone, microcontroller, Unmanned Underwater vehicles (UUV).

I. INTRODUCTION

The drone market has grown at a blistering tempo since 2015. The principle drivers behind this extraordinary increase are the important subclass of underwater drones also named as Unmanned Underwater vehicles (UUV). UUV were initially designed as army mine-sweepers, business purposes and navigate in water bodies. UUV is classified into two main classes: Remotely Operated UUV (ROV) and Autonomous UUV (AUV).

Era of Drones

With the advancement of technology of UUV has gained international fame to its credit. Many evolved international locations have already commenced their everyday drones for different possibilities like tracking, home delivery, surveying and so on. One of the most usual technological vehicles currently in use today are Unmanned Underwater vehicles (UUV) or Unmanned Submersible automobiles (USV) and Unmanned Aerial automobiles (UAV).

Amphibious Drones

With the advancement in the latest technologies drones now have the capability to fly and navigate in air and water. A few research projects by international universities have seen this development.

The UAVs we want to build can be used in underwater and air operations, UAVs with this capability can cover many areas and perform dangerous operations. AUV), the difference between the two is that ROV operates according to the command of the operator while AUV operates according to the command of the operator. This table 1 summarizes the existing techniques used in amphibious drone design, highlighting their respective advantages and disadvantages.

As a result, the primary goal of this research is to build a prototype of an amphibious drone. The main purpose of this drone will be to help the defence services to detect movement of enemy submarines, submersible vehicles and mines as well as aerial operations like detecting enemy ships and boats. We plan on achieving this feat by using SONAR technology underwater and image detection for aerial purposes. This project is one-of-a-kind invention which has multiple uses apart from the defence services. This project is built using waterproof motors to power the Unmanned Vehicle which can provide enough thrust to navigate in air as well as underwater, this drone will be controlled by a microcontroller on board which stabilises its speed and operations, a sensor will be used to detect the medium it is working in. When underwater, SONAR will be used to map the sea

surface and process that data to find the submarines. Aerially a Raspberry Pi Cam module will be used to detect the images and process it with a specified dataset to identify the boats and ships.

Table 1: Comparative Analysis of Existing Techniques for Amphibious Drone

Technique	Advantages	Disadvantages
Buoyancy control	- Enables navigation in water and air	- Requires careful balance and symmetry for stability
Radio signals	- Effective communication in aerial and aquatic modes	- Signal penetration and attenuation challenges
Acoustic communications	- Reliable communication underwater	- Limited range and bandwidth
Microcontroller	- Efficient drone control and data management	- Adds weight and complexity to the drone
Aluminum alloy	- Provides durability and protection against damage	- May add weight to the drone
Hybrid cylinder design	- Balances weight and performance in a compact structure	- Design complexity may increase
Simulations and testing	- Allows for validation and optimization of designs	- Requires resources for testing and analysis
Computer-aided technology	- Facilitates stress and deflection analysis	- Requires specialized software and expertise

Research Motivation

The changing needs of contemporary defense and emergency response situations are the driving force behind research on unmanned amphibious vehicles, with a multifaceted focus on image identification, airborne search and rescue, and underwater stealth against radar. The capacity to move fluidly between the air and water domains is critical for mission accomplishment in modern naval operations. Unmanned amphibious vehicles offer a novel approach to this problem by fusing the benefits of quick response and overhead surveillance with the ability to travel underwater. By using cutting-edge image detection technology, the vehicle can precisely identify and track targets in a variety of situations while also improving its situational awareness during reconnaissance. Furthermore, to ensure the vehicle's secret activities, it is important to have underwater stealth capabilities against radar detection, offering a tactically advantageous strategic position. By pushing the limits of autonomous amphibious systems, this research hopes to create a comprehensive platform that can perform well in both covert underwater operations and aerial search and rescue missions. This will advance Defense and emergency response capabilities in challenging and dynamic environments.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of Proposed System

D. Research Contribution

This review aims to provide an overview of current research, covering all aspects of drone technology and object detection. A systematic review carried out in this study is highlighted as follows:

- Provide a low-cost unique drone which can be used by our defence organizations for various activities in research and surveillance.
- Categorize existing works by traditional image processing or deep learning and immediate exploitation methods.
- Provide a simpler approach in existing technology to assist more researchers in this field.

The remaining part of the article is organized as follows: Section 2 explores the related works. Section 3 presents the outcome of literature review. The discussion about the existing methods is presented in section 4. Section 5 concludes the article.

II. RELATED WORKS

Researchers have conducted numerous studies on drones, some emphasizing their applications, while others focus on the methods used in drone research. Lin Meng et al. (2018) created an open-source underwater drone intended to perform the task of fish recognition using deep learning. The drone, based on Raspberry Pi, features open-source hardware designs and achieved automatic diving in natural lakes, producing accurate panoramic images and an 87% fish recognition accuracy. S. Nithya et al. (2022) introduced a versatile, remotely operated vehicle (ROV) designed for both land and water applications. Controlled by a human operator, the ROV offers real-time monitoring of water parameters and can inspect underwater structures, check oil ship hulls, assess bridges, study water quality during construction, explore marine life, and serve as a landmine detection decoy for the military. Built with PVC pipes and steel rods, the ROV is affordable, low-maintenance, and features sensors connected to a Raspberry Pi model 3B. Wenhui Wang et al. (2009) developed a low-cost UUV for surface level water tasks like ship sea chest inspection. The PVC-hulled UUV features horizontal propellers, vertical thrusters, and on-board sensors. Pengfei Liu et al. (2016) aimed to enhance unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) by developing a flight control system using Digital Signal Processor (DSP) technology.

Emphasizing small size, cost-effectiveness, and reusability, the study addresses challenges in achieving autonomous flight. By incorporating adaptive control theory, the project leverages DSP's processing speed and accuracy, overcoming limitations of traditional control algorithms for improved UAV control. Balasubramanian Esakki et al. (2018) developed a versatile unmanned amphibious vehicle merging multi-rotor UAV and hovercraft capabilities for diverse missions. Conducted finite element analysis for structural strength and computational fluid dynamics for drag assessment. Successfully tested a 7kg payload prototype for stable flight and water operations. Implemented an IoT-based system for water quality measurement in lakes, emphasizing disaster mission applications. Dinesh Manoharan et al. (2021) developed an autonomous amphibious unmanned aerial vehicle (AAUAV) with a hybrid multicopter-hovercraft design for water-based applications. Calculated parameters, selected a propulsion system, and created a 3D CAD model. Fabricated and tested a prototype, confirming successful functionality through trial runs and ground/field tests. Surendar Ganesan et al. (2021) presented a systematic conceptual design for an Unmanned Amphibious Aerial Vehicle (UAAV) aimed at water quality assessment. Integrated hovercraft and multi-rotor systems for remote water sample collection. Overcame design challenges using scenario-based methods and computational analysis. The experimental prototype demonstrated successful flying and hovering capabilities in field trials.

Xu et. al.,[1] designed autonomous drone navigation based on aerial vision and deep learning able to deliver emergency supplies, put out the fire, and transporting victims by air. It uses rotating cameras and onboard processing modules to navigate tragedies with a drone. Guan H et. al.,[2] presented YOLOv4 algorithm for object detection. The idea of a flight path strategy for UAVs proved to save time and energy. The major contribution of the work is to provide a latest perspective on current drone inspections and discuss potential lidar-assisted smart power line inspection concepts. Efaz E T et. al.,[3] presented a drone technology to compare plenty of different cameras that are used for the inspection process. Moreover, this study encourages safety during the inspection process without involving human subjects to physically inspect it. Roy Edgar Hansen et al.,[4] explored a unique Underwater acoustics method for transmitting messages over long distances in the ocean. The authors focused on the basics of sonar, which amplifies the weak sound waves that are affected by changes in the speed of sound with increased depth, resulting in strong sound waves. The ocean is a lossy acoustic environment, limiting the distance over which the sound can travel. Haeseng yang et al.,[5], highlighted the latest machine learning techniques and active sonar systems for performing identification and classification tasks. Used the input from generated noise and scattered signal from the target, signal processing technology, acoustic modelling and machine learning algorithms together, to improve the performance of the system. Target detection works based on machine learning to gather sufficient information about target and provide location-specific results at that moment. This method minimizes false alarms resulting from collisions with characteristics similar to the target signal.

Maruis Zieja et. al.,[6], presented a paper discussing the importance of acquiring images from underwater vehicles (AUVs) for seafloor mapping. While 3D multibeam sonar can provide many measurement points, the analysis of information gathered by side-scan sonar during an AUV mission has not yet been investigated. Data collection is done using an image capture application. Maximillia hell et. al.,[7], presented a design of a movable drone that can be utilized by the learners to learn and practice the basics of drone operation. The UUV design is based on the notion of Y6 polar system. The system is foldable and waterproof according to DIN EN 60529 (IP01) standard. The system is capable of producing a maximum take-off weight

(MTOM) of about 5 kg at altitude and the discussed about the optimal design of the propeller. Zhu Qiang et. al.,[8] have proposed two Unmanned Sea Vehicle (USV) control systems. First, the hardware structure of the USV control system is introduced. Then a mathematical model of a boat based on a catamaran was created, which served as the basis for the study of control algorithms. Liu Pengfei et. al.,[9] provided a comprehensive overview and development perspective for addressing weaknesses in computational management. With the development of the aerospace domain, the design, implementation and use of UAVs are attracting increasing versatility, reusability and other features. Flight control is an important tool in ensuring flight control of UAVs. Many forces and devices used to reduce flight risks have become important issues. Although the need for flight control has increased in terms of planning speed and miniaturization, the risk of development and the fact that it does not require spending a lot of money on businesses and assets in real time have become an important issue in its development. Adopting DSP based flight control has provided an alternative effective solution.

Wang, W.H. et. al.,[10] presented a cheaper UUV model designed for shallow water operations, specifically the inspection and maintenance of marine tanks for biosecurity purposes. Wang Wenhui et. al.,[11], proposed a UUV prototype designed for shallow water operations, particularly for analyzing and mapping sea conditions on ships for biosecurity purposes. Suresh et. al.,[12] have explored the design of amphibious drones that can fly in the air and in water. The system used radio signal communications. To effectively control the movement of the drone, the microcontroller is utilized as the flight controller to send and record the stored data. The proposed amphibious drone is tested its effectiveness in air and water. Wang Hong-Jian et. al.,[13] designed an Small Unmanned Aquatic Vehicle(SUUV) for monitoring the water bodies. Finally, results from software simulation convey that the SUV meets the design requirements in terms of body planning, high shell design, safety measures and power generation. Philip B. Chappell et. al.,[14], pointed out about processing of images collected through sonar from stationary Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs). The work aimed at detecting objects such as seabed mines and people. The work resulted in a software that uses machine learning techniques to identify mine in side-scan sonar images and analyze the collected data. P. Chappell et. al.,[15] presented pointed out that the military is increasingly using UUVs to obtain high-resolution sonar images to detect coastal mines and other works of interest. The authors focused on the distribution technologies for side-view sonar mounted on UUVs.

Amphibious drones are the drones of the future, they possess the capability to disrupt the current defence drone technology and provide a multi-array of features in just one single device. The key applications of the amphibious drones are as follows:

A. Surveillance

Researchers proposed the hybrid drone surveillance system which is intended to monitor human activities. SSD extracts spatial features and LSTM extracts temporal features. This function achieves good results in data streaming[16]. Performed target detection in drone video using the Yolo V2 deep learning algorithm on the Nvidia Jetson TX2 GPU platform. The author proposes early warning as a result of the homing model[17]. Explored deep learning techniques to learn to detect people and numbers in drone videos. The authors tested two methods, namely VGG19 with fast mapping and fast RCNN with ResNet as the backbone. This study concludes that VGG19 outperforms Faster RCNN when the population is dense[18]. Proposed a deep model consisting of CNN pre-training, CNN supervisor, and HELM to detect people in drone videos. The main advantage of this work is that the model is strong in terms of location, colour, height and direction[19],[20],[21]. Proposed a system that can identify and identify adjacent objects as ship and non-ship. In this study, one of the most advanced neural network-based object detection algorithms was used to detect ships from photographs and videos taken from the sea. The "preparatory model" captures all kinds of floating objects and turns them into ships, speedboats, buoys, etc.[22],[23],[24],[25]. It is training that uses publicly available maritime data, which can be classified into ten specific types, such as: The model outperforms the object model used in marine object search. It also has a frame rate of around 30 frames per second.

B. Remote Decoy Deployment

The modern warships and submarines are the most advanced marine vehicles in use, these vehicles use the most advanced technology. Submarines are prone to torpedo and mine attacks underwater, to tackle which DRDO (Defence Research and Development Organization, Ministry of Defence, Government of India) has developed a system named Anti Torpedo Decoy System which uses SONAR technology to scramble the torpedoes signals and mis-guide it. Our proposed system can be used to deploy these Decoys at the most remote locations underwater. The pick and drop feature of our drone allows the operator to navigate and place decoy traps in the remote seas without any hassle[26],[27],[28],[29].

III. RESEARCH GAP AND DISCUSSION

From the above survey so far, various image processing techniques capable of identifying, locating drones are discussed[30],[31],[32]. The Table 1 has the complete description of the papers surveyed with the required parameters and also the efficiency of the experiments conducted[33],[34],[35],[36].

From the Table 2 shown below we explore the various existing methodologies and note down the metrics, advantages, and disadvantages[37],[38],[39].

Table 2. Summary of existing works on amphibious drones and object detection in drone images.

Sl. No.	Author & Year	Objective	Methodology	Approach	Advantages	Disadvantages	Metric
1	Liguo Tan et al. (2023)	Amphibious Multi-rotor UAV out-of-water control.	ADRC position and elevation controller is generated by the ADRC algorithm.	ADRC algorithm	Easy transition between water and air.	Chances of failure during water discharge	Control performance
2	Shubo Xu et al.(2023)	Review and analysis of deep learning-based underwater object detection.	Integration of underwater image enhancement and object detection with experimental validation	Identification of challenges and integration of image enhancement.	Real time processing and deep learning capabilities.	Dependance on data quality and limited labeled data.	Precision and sensitivity.
3	Vedanshu Dewangan et al. (2023)	To improve the accuracy of small UAV detection	UAV detection using deep-learning and distance wise analysis	YOLO v5	They can be controlled remotely on the go or pre-programmed to fly independently of the trip.	Drone detection with lower confidence scores and false detection	Precision, confidence score and IoU threshold
4	Mariusz Zieja, et al. (2022)	Image acquisition from AUV	Location of the operating area, AUV altitude, AUV speed, direction, water depth, speed of sound in water (SVP) and theoretical range of the sonar.	Three-D Multibeam Sonar	Many measurement points can be obtained by recording the seafloor using 3D multibeam sonar. Create a collection of documents using the application as a function of the screenshot.	The limitations of small hardware, such as computational performance and battery power, reduce the possibility of running deep learning models on board.	Precision recall
5	Dr. S. Nithya et al. (2022)	Land and underwater rover using Raspberry -Pi.	Raspberry Pi based system using BLDC motors and PVC pipes, camera is used for navigation.	Ultrasonic navigation	It can be used on both land and sea so no Hassel of keeping two devices for different purposes.	Lesser durability because of PVC structure.	Precision
6	Pier Luigi Mazzeo et.al (2022)	Underwater Acoustic Research Trends with Machine Learning: Active SONAR Application	Datasets, Convolution neural network, YOLO algorithms, Region based CNN.	CNN and YOLO	The main purpose of this article is to evaluate search objects for ship detection from satellite images. Check out YOLOv3 and YOLOv4.	Sensors such as SARs under extreme conditions has to be tested as visible spectrum imagery is unavailable.	Dataset
7	M. Arun Kumar et al. (2021)	Amphibious UAV for horticulture.	Automation engineering utilized for cutting the plants in less time and less power,	Thrust estimation	Plants cutting done in less time and power, hence diminishing the contamination that happens by using the fuels.	Cutting on highways makes more accidental cases	Precision and loss
8	EFAZ, E. T. et al.(2021)	Surveillance	Degree of freedom, control system architecture, flight code model.	First person view(FPV) mini camera generating live video.	The drone design is cheaper and can fly at a maximum speed of 53.3 ms ⁻¹ , weigh less than 1 kg and move for more than 16.4 minutes. By integrating the action camera, the aircraft can be used for aerial	Restrictions on specifications for larger size, smaller height and smaller aid.	-

					photography as well as drone racing or package delivery.		
9	H Guan et al.(2021)	Potential lidar supported intelligent powerline inspection concept.	Lidar supported route generation.	Accurate powerline inspections.	The standard procedure for lidar-assisted smart power line inspection includes four data analysis steps: point cloud classification, key point extraction, road construction experience and fault finding.	Limited power supply during inspection reduces efficiency.	Accuracy
10	Daniel Porras et al.(2021)	Drone magnetometry in mining research.	Equipped with GSMP-35U GEM-systems potassium vapor magnetometer.	Magnetometry	Accurate detection of Cu-Co-Ni.	Limited to only the three metals.	TMF and TMFRP
11	Zhenxing Ming et al. (2021)	Collision free navigation of a Quadcopter UAV among moving obstacles.	3D vision cone-based reactive navigation algorithm.	Vision cone	Collision free movement using movement.	Accuracy is lower when facing densely placed obstacles.	3D Vision
12	Haesang Yang, et al.(2020)	Target detection and classification.	AUV and Automatic target recognition system.	Active SONAR signal processing.	Sonar systems generally use signals emitted by sound waves and scattered by targets, complementing existing signal generation techniques, acoustic modeling and machine learning to produce results that are more effective in many aspects, such as sound characteristics, target characteristics and target/Clutter signal characteristics.	It is difficult to effectively handle image resolution and classification in real-time using machine learning for automatic product recognition.	Precision, loss and accuracy

IV. CONCLUSION

Optimizing the hull design with a high-density and low-volume configuration will effectively reduce center change time. Conversely, a low-volume and high-density hull configuration results in decreased buoyancy. Therefore, the primary objective of the UAV model's design is to minimize all sources of drag to enhance vehicle acceleration. This involves considering both mechanical and drone design aspects. To achieve superior performance, it's crucial to minimize drag induced by the drone's structure. This means reducing the drone's frontal area to minimize drag, which in turn improves overall speed and reduces energy consumption. Additionally, incorporating a hybrid cylinder design allows the quadcopter to achieve a balance between low weight and high performance within a compact framework. To validate these design principles, simulations, virtual prototyping, and immediate testing are essential. Computer-aided technology facilitates stress and deflection tests on the frame, yielding satisfactory results.

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